

Pepper Powdery mildew: Understanding the cause and combating through resistance breeding

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Abstract

Peppers, hot and sweet, botanically called as *Capsicum annuum* L. are important vegetable crops in India. Powdery mildew caused by *Leveillula taurica* is one of the major diseases that affects chillies and can cause yield losses of 14-80%. The disease causes defoliation and decreased fruit yield. The disease initially appears as yellow chlorotic spots on the upper surface and white powdery growth on the lower surface. It has wide host range and develops under 10-32°C and wide range of humidity conditions. Several resistant genotypes have been found in different *Capsicum* spp. Studies revealed that dominant and polygenes control resistance. Utilization of resistant sources is essential for effective disease control.

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Introduction

Pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.) is an economically important vegetable and spice crop that is widely grown in India as well as in tropical and subtropical regions. Its principal use is as a spice in various cuisines and sauces. Bell pepper is a remunerative crop grown both under open field and protected structures. These crops have great potential in domestic markets as well as for export. Chilli suffers from many foliar diseases like *Cercospora* leaf spot, powdery mildew, anthracnose, murda complex. Powdery mildew of chilli, caused by *Leveillula taurica* is a serious problem in India. The disease can lead to significant yield losses of 14-80%. Severe defoliation results in leaf drop, reduced photosynthetic activity and decrease in fruit size as well as the number of fruits produced per plant. (Mathur *et al.*, 1972 and Sudha and Lakshmanan 2007).

History and distribution

Salmon (1906) taxonomically classified the species *Leveillula taurica*, a member of family Erysiphaceae based on endophytism of the fungus and morphological features of conidia. Arnaud (1921) established the genus *Leveillula*. The occurrence of *L. taurica* on chilli in India was reported by Butler (1918)

and later by Uppal *et al.*, 1934. Until 1970s, it was considered as minor disease but of late, the disease is gaining more importance and cause considerable damage in the farmers' fields, particularly under moderate temperature and humid conditions. It is especially devastating under protected cultivation structures. The disease has been reported from almost all the major pepper growing states of India *viz.*, Karnataka (Bidari *et al.*, 1985), Maharashtra (Joi and Sonone, 1980), Tamil Nadu (Sivaprakasam *et al.*, 1976), Andhra Pradesh (Sitarama Raju and Srinivasa Rao, 1981), Jaipur (Mathur *et al.*, 1972), Madhya Pradesh (Keshwal and Choubay, 1983) and Rajasthan (Saroj Singh and Satish Lodha, 1985).

Symptomatology

Powdery mildew appears first on older leaves and then progresses to younger plants in chilli. The ventral surface of the leaves has chlorotic patches, while the dorsal surface is coated with white to grey powdery fungus development. Later, the lower surface of the leaves becomes necrotic as well. Powdery mildew infection causes leaf shedding, which results in significant yield

losses due to reduced number of fruits and size (McGrath et al., 2001 and Parisi et al., 2020).

The pathogen- Morphology

Leveillula taurica is an obligate fungal pathogen, from the Phylum: Ascomycota, Order: Erysiphales and Family: Erysiphaceae. The mycelium of powdery mildew was endophytic bearing hyaline conidiophores on the leaf surface. Conidia of *L. taurica* on chilli are typically dimorphic, often long and borne singly or in chains (Correll et al., 1987). Shape of conidia is reported to be pyriform and cylindrical. The pyriform conidia have a size of 80.4 - 49.8 µm x 25.5 - 11.7 µm and cylindrical conidia ranged between 64.3 - 39.1 µm x 20.1 - 9.7 µm. (Boesewinkel, 1980).

Host range

Leveillula taurica has wide host range including cotton, onion, artichoke, potato, eggplant, peppers, tomatoes and some of weed sps. (Correll et al., 1987 and Khodaparast et al., 2001)

Epidemiology of powdery mildew disease

It is observed that the incidence of powdery mildew on chilli appears in field when atmospheric temperature ranged between 10-32°C. The maximum conidial germination occurs when the temperature ranges between 18 and 25°C. Conidial viability declined as temperatures increase above 30°C. Reports have proved that conidia of *L. taurica* could germinate under wide range of RH i.e., 30-100% (Clerk and Ayesu, 1967 and Elad et al., 2007).

Resistant sources against powdery mildew of chilli

Transferring disease resistance from wild relatives into widely grown cultivars significantly improves yield and fruit quality. Sources of resistance to many pepper diseases have been identified in different wild species and these traits have been effectively introgressed into commercial cultivars. Some varieties resistant to powdery mildew are listed below.

Sl. No.	Resistant varieties	Reference
1.	Puri orange-2, EC-21660, Puri red, EC-31308, EC-34242, Puri orange-1	Bidari et al., 1985
2.	PMR – 10/95 K, IIHR –1238	Murthy and Deshpande, 1997
3.	MS-2 x PMR-76, MS-3 x PMR-76	Reddy et al., 2002
4.	Hv-12, # 124 and Chili	Blat et al., 2005
5.	PBC972 x PMR39	Krishna et al., 2006
6.	Nandi, Phule Jyoti, Orissa Local, Arka Suphal	Wankhade and Mohir, 2015
7.	Arka Harita, Arka Suphal, PBC167 (VI046819)	Rao and Anilkumar, 2020
8.	Ag-01, Ag-02, A-06, A-23	Manzo et al., 2021
9.	JNA1 × Mattur Local, JNA1 × G4, JNA1 × GCV111, JNA1 × Rajput Yellow	Umesh Babu et al., 2023

Genetics of powdery mildew

Inheritance of resistance to powdery mildew is complex and least understood. Powdery mildew resistance in pepper has been reported to be a dominant and polygenic trait (Murthy & Deshpande, 1997; Blat et al., 2005; Krishna et al., 2006 and Jo et al., 2017). Genetic studies have further suggested that resistance to powdery mildew is governed by fewer genes showing notable additive and epistatic interactions in different pepper genetic backgrounds (Daubeze et al., 1995 and Krishna et al., 2006). A single dominant locus, *PMR1* located in Chr 4 responsible for powdery mildew resistance has been reported (Jo et al., 2017). *PMR1* locus has been identified from population between *C. baccatum* and *C. annuum*

supporting the introgression of resistance from *C. baccatum*, possibly using *C. chinense* as a bridge species (Parisi et al., 2020). Pepper genotypes with different levels of resistance to powdery mildew have been reported among several *Capsicum* species like *C. annuum*, *C. baccatum*, *C. frutescens* and *C. chinense* (Ullasa et al., 1981 and Deshpande et al., 1985). The inheritance obtained by virus-induced gene silencing indicates that pepper's susceptibility to *L. taurica* may involve both *CaMlo1* and *CaMlo2* genes. According to Zheng et al. 2013, the *CaMlo2* gene is transcriptionally responsive to *L. taurica* host tissue penetration and either *CaMlo1* or *CaMlo2* silencing decreases *L. taurica* susceptibility of pepper. These results provided evidence

that the susceptibility to *L. taurica* is controlled by at least one pepper *Mlo* homolog (McCoy & Bosland, 2019 and Parisi et al., 2020).

Conclusion

Powdery mildew is a major disease of pepper that causes serious yield loss. The fungus survives under

a wide range of temperature and humidity conditions, making it difficult to control. Many resistant varieties and genetic sources have been identified and studies shows that resistance is mainly governed by dominant and polygenic genes. Therefore, developing resistant cultivars is the most effective and sustainable way to manage powdery mildew disease in pepper.

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